

PROPELLER INFLUENCE ON SURFACE PRESSURE FLUCTUATION UNDER BOUNDARY LAYER INGESTION CONDITION

Leandro Alan Castelucci¹
University of Twente
Drienerlolaan 5, 7522 NB Enschede - Netherlands

Cornelis H. Venner²
University of Twente
Drienerlolaan 5, 7522 NB Enschede - Netherlands

ABSTRACT

Research on propeller noise under boundary layer ingestion condition is essential for designing new aircraft concepts. Measurements of pressure spectra on a flat plate below a propeller give important information about the noise coming from the blades. These also are important for designing surface noise mitigation structures, such as acoustic black holes, meta-materials, and liners. This paper investigates the effects of a propeller on the flat plate surface pressure under boundary layer ingestion, using bottom of the wind tunnel channel as flat plate. Tripping devices on the wind tunnel bottom wall control the boundary layer thicknesses. The surface pressure is measured using an instrumented plate positioned underneath the propeller. The plate has 87 pressure taps to measure the unsteady and steady pressure using the remote microphone probe (RMP) technique. The results show the influence of the propeller inflow, the advance ratio, and the number of blades on the different regions underneath the propeller, and on coherent turbulent structures of the incoming flow. The boundary layer thicknesses affects the static pressure upstream of the propeller - creating high pressure regions. The propeller affects the turbulent structures downstream of the blades, increasing its correlation length.

1. INTRODUCTION

Reducing aircraft noise in near urban areas requires advances in noise mitigation techniques, even more so for new designs and concepts of aircraft. Several new concept designs include the boundary layer ingestion. When close to the airframe, the propulsive system ingests the wake or boundary layer, which possibly generating a performance benefit [1]. However, the potential increase in performance can be detrimental to the noise levels, as the rotor or propeller blades are now passing through a non-uniform flow, increasing its noise [2]. One way to mitigate noise from rotating blades is to use shrouding [3]. This technique influences the directivity and reduces possible noise reflections from the rotor. However shrouding is not always an option in design.

In many areas of aeronautics unsteady wall pressure measurements are used, e.g. for boundary layer characterization [4], and leading edge noise [5]. When the propeller is over a flat plate, the

¹l.a.castelucci@utwente.nl

²c.h.venner@utwente.nl

reflections from the plate highly influence the directivity perpendicular to the plate [6, 7]. These reflections can be absorbed by the use of specific techniques such as liners, foams, and metamaterials. However, to properly design and dimension the noise-absorbing structures, a thorough examination of the effects of the propeller on the flow over the surface has to be executed.

The goal of the current work is to understand the effects of boundary layer ingestion by a propeller on the impinging flow by analysis of the surface pressure fluctuations on the flat plate close to the propeller, and radiated noise.

2. REMOTE MICROPHONE PROBES

Microphones are commonly used to measure unsteady pressure fluctuations, e.g. in wind tunnel tests. A crucial aspect of the design of any experimental setup is the microphone mounting. Flush-mounted microphones are used when the array has sufficient size for mounting the transducers [8], and it is big enough for accounting discrete points. Examples of the flush-mounted microphones are ducted fan noise measurements [9, 10] and wind tunnel wall measurements [11]. Mounting the microphone under a pinhole with the microphone under a recess, connected to the surface through a small hole - reduces the attenuation due to the microphone surface area [12, 13]. This mounting also allows closer proximity to the surface acquisition points, necessary in research requiring, for example, higher resolution as turbulent boundary layer characterization [14], and wall pressure fluctuations on trailing edge [15].

This research uses the remote microphone probe (RMP) technique for three reasons. Firstly, the limited thickness of the instrumented plate to position recessed microphones. Also, the proximity requirement of some pinholes would require a more complex plate design if the microphones were to be inside the plate. Manufacturing the instrumented plate is much simpler as it requires only the drilling of the pressure taps. Lastly, the acquisition of unsteady and static pressure can be done in parallel, which is achieved by connecting the end tubing of the RMP to a pressure scanner.

Figure 1 shows the setup of the RMP. The guiding tubes are the interconnection between the pinhole and the microphone. The pressure fluctuations passing through the pinhole propagate along the tubing, behaving as sound waves. The guiding tubes bring those propagating waves to the microphone - hence the name *remote*. The microphone acquires the sound wave that continues through the long tube. This termination is long enough that the wave dissipates through viscous losses, and there are no reflections on the measuring microphone.

The tubing dimensions are defined depending on design requirements and the position of the remote microphone. There is an influence of the length of the tubing and the diameter of the pin on the attenuation and characteristics of the waves inside the RMP [8, 13, 16].

Figure 1: Remote microphone probe schematics.

2.1. Calibration

The waves inside the RMP undergo viscous losses, related to the geometry, the length and diameter of the tubing, and the transitions between the connections of the ducts. Setups with different measuring points may also have differences related to manufacturing, due to the attenuation of each microphone probe. A calibration method for the RMP is necessary to account for the attenuation of each different microphone in the system.

The calibration used in this experiment is based on the two-step calibration technique described in [13] and [16]. The calibration requires a calibrator piece that has a reference microphone. The reference microphone signal is then compared with a flush-mounted microphone with a transfer function. This transfer function is the ratio between the auto-spectral density of both signals. The second transfer function is the relation between the auto-spectral density of the signals between the reference microphone and the actual RMP.

$$TF_{wall,rmp} = \frac{TF_{ref,rmp}}{TF_{ref,wall}}. \quad (1)$$

The transfer function in Equation 1 expresses the ratio between the wall pressure fluctuations and the measurement in the remote microphone probes. This relation is used to convert the results of the RMP, considering the attenuation caused by the setup. This transfer function can only be applied for frequencies where the coherence between the signals is close to unity ($\gamma^2 = 1$). Figure 2 shows the signals before and after calibration.

Figure 2: Calibration routine. (a) Both signals from the reference microphone and the RMP are acquired. (b) The transfer function $TF_{wall,rmp}$ is applied and the resulting signal is then compared with the reference. For the frequencies above 6000 Hz, the calibration loses reliability, for those are frequencies where the coherence between the signals is not close to unity.

3. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

The measurements took place in the aeroacoustic wind tunnel of the University of Twente. The facility consists of a closed-loop wind tunnel with its test section inside an anechoic chamber. The wind tunnel has a $0.7 \times 0.9 m^2$ rectangular test section, with possibilities of testing in a fully closed or semi-open test configuration. The flow speed in the test section can get up to 60 m/s. The turbulence intensity level is below 0.08% [17]. The anechoic chamber is $6 \times 6 \times 4 m^3$, equipped with commercial wedges on the walls and absorbers on the other surfaces, achieving a cut-off frequency of 160 Hz.

The boundary layer ingestion is reproduced by approaching the propeller along the bottom surface of the wind tunnel (Figure 3). This surface is a flat plate on which the boundary layer develops and hits the propeller disk area. The boundary layer develops from the end of the contraction of the

wind tunnel until the propeller blades plane, resulting in a distance of 3.62 meters. Tripping devices manipulate the boundary layer thicknesses (Figure 3). The trip devices are 60 ° zigzag strips, as this geometry causes a faster transition. [18–20] and is suited for a long development distance. Table 1 shows the characteristics of the boundary layer of each tripping device.

Figure 3: Schematics of the configuration (side view, x-z plane). The tripping device is positioned at the end of the contraction of the wind tunnel - the beginning of the flat surface. The boundary layer develops from the tripping device to the propeller plane. Different heights of the tripping device result in different boundary layer thicknesses at the point of impingement.

Three different propellers are analyzed in this experiment. The first is a 2-bladed, 12" x 18" Mejzlik propeller. The other two are 12" x 12" Mejzlik propellers, three and five-bladed. The geometries are based on the *SilentProp* project [21]. The three sets of blades generate data on: the effect of loading using the same diameter and different pitch; the effect of solidity using the same pitch-to-diameter ratio, and the effect of the number of blades.

Table 1: Boundary layer characteristics for each tripping device. δ is the boundary layer thickness, δ/D is the immersion ratio, $H = \delta^*/\theta$ is the shape factor (δ^* is the displacement thickness and θ is the momentum thickness), Re_x is the Reynolds of the stream-wise position from the tripping X, and Re_θ is the Reynolds number for the momentum thickness

Trip	δ, mm	δ/D	H	Re_x	Re_θ
Trip 0	54.5	0.18	1.32	7.28×10^6	18550
Trip 1	102.5	0.34	1.27	7.29×10^6	22370
Trip 2	139.8	0.46	1.24	6.82×10^6	33920

Pressure fluctuations are acquired using an instrumented plate beneath the propeller. The plate acquires the pressure by 0.5 mm diameter pinholes attached to a remote microphone probe setup through a 1.6 mm channel. Figure 4 shows the schematic of the plate with the positions of the pinholes.

Each individual pinhole leads to a *Knowles FG-23329-P07* microphone installed inside a Plexiglas structure. These microphones are connected to a *PXIe-4499* Sound and Vibration module (NI PXIe-1073 chassis). The span-wise distribution of points on the instrumented plate follows the

Figure 4: Instrumented plate pinhole positions (top view, x-y plane). For reference, X is the stream-wise direction and Y is the span-wise direction. D is the propeller diameter. The markers represents the pinhole positions. The central rectangle shows the propeller wetted area.

potential function of Equation 2:

$$y/y_{min} = (y_{max}/y_{min})^{(i-2)/(N-2)}, i = 2, \dots, N. \quad (2)$$

This distribution is proposed by [12], and ensures an irregular distribution of distances between the acquisition points which leads to the maximum number of point-by-point spacial distances possible when comparing the coherence and cross-correlations. The points are evenly distributed stream-wise, so many sections downstream and upstream of the propeller plane can be analyzed. Steady pressures are measured by connecting the anechoic end of the RMP setup to the pressure scanner *NetScanner 9216*.

The microphone pressure acquisition time is 30 seconds, at an acquisition frequency of 2^{16} Hz. The spectral density is calculated using Welch's periodogram method, with a Hanning window of 2^{13} blocks and 50% overlap. In this case, the bin resolution is 8 Hz. The static pressure acquisition time is 10 seconds at a 100 Hz acquisition frequency.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section shows the static and unsteady pressure the results for the instrumented flat plate. For reference, the results show the top view of the propeller, using the same reference frame as Figure 4. The flow direction is top to bottom, so $x/D > 0$ is upstream, and $x/D < 0$ is downstream. The red rectangle represents the propeller region. The left side of the propeller region, negative y/D , is rotating away from the plate, and the right side of the propeller region is rotating towards the plate (counterclockwise rotation). Pressure results are scaled with the wind tunnel speed: $C_p = (p - p_\infty)/(0.5 \times \rho_\infty \times U_\infty^2)$

4.1. Static pressure

Data from the static measurements show the distribution of high and low-pressure regions under the propeller at different times. The different pressure regions are well-defined spatially (see Figures 5 and 6. These regions of high-low pressure oscillate periodically.

First, the effect of the number of blades is analyzed. The results for the 3-bladed and 5-bladed propeller are shown in Figure 5 and Figure 6. In both cases, there is a small high-pressure region downstream of the right blade. This region agrees with the pressure side of the propeller blades ($0 < x/D < -0.1$). However, the high pressure does not extend fully on the right side blade, showing that the blade effectiveness is lower as it approaches the tip. This can be caused by the velocity infield being non-optimal for the profile on the propeller blades.

Figure 5: Static pressure distribution over time (3-bladed propeller, 6500 rpm, $J = 0.90$, $\delta/D = 0.18$). The data at 0.02 seconds show a high pressure at the right tip and on the pressure side of the propeller blade. A vortex-like structure is forming, as can be seen by the two high pressure region downstream of the propeller.

Figure 6: Static pressure distribution over time (5-bladed propeller, 6500 rpm, $J = 0.90$, $\delta/D = 0.18$).

Upstream of the blades ($0 < x/D < 0.1$), the low pressure agrees with the suction side of the profiles. There is an intensity difference between the down-blade and the up-blade, as shown in the second frame of both Figures 5 and 6. This difference in intensity is because the propeller influences the incoming flow, giving it an initial swirl close to the propeller plane. Upstream of the left blades is a region of high pressure that remains stable during the acquisition time. There is a periodic intensity reduction, as seen in the time-frames of 0.20 s and 0.50 s. Overall the static pressure oscillates periodically throughout the measurements. The suction side low pressure (right blades, upstream) of the 5-bladed propeller is more intense in comparison with the 3-bladed propeller. The upstream high pressure at the left blade oscillation has a 0.4 second period for the 5-bladed propeller and a 0.3 second period for the 3-bladed propeller. High-Low oscillations on the downstream pressure occurs every 0.02 seconds for both propellers.

The number of blades, and therefore the loading and the solidity, affects the intensity of these high-pressure regions, as can be seen in Figure 7. Figure 8 shows the boundary layer thickness influence. Those results are the time-averaged data for each pressure port. The increase of the boundary layer size impinging on the propeller blades affects mainly the intensity of the pressure distribution. As can be seen, the intensity of the downstream vortex formation, and the suction region upstream of the right-side blades (moving towards the plate) increases. The tip vortices also show increasing intensity with increasing boundary layer thickness.

Figure 7: Time-averaged pressure distribution for different number of blades ($\delta/D = 0.18$, 6500 RPM, $J = 0.90$)

Figure 8: Time-averaged pressure distribution for different boundary layer thicknesses (2-Bladed propeller, 6000 rpm, $J = 0.98$).

4.2. Unsteady pressure

The unsteady pressure measured by the remote microphone probes gives information about the surface pressure fluctuations on the measurement plate. Given the results for the static pressure, it is clear that the propeller affects the flow upstream and downstream of the propeller. Upstream the flow is getting influenced by the high-pressure spots forming due to the fast passing of the blades. Downstream, the propeller already acted on the flow, so there are the rotating characteristics of vortices. For the analysis of the surface pressure fluctuations, two regions are studied. Upstream and downstream of the propeller position, and right and left regions of the plate.

Propeller noise is analyzed with the spectra of the microphone measurements. However, showing those results for all pressure taps would be inconvenient and difficult to assess. An alternative would be understanding the effects of the propeller on turbulent structures. That may be a

good indicator of how the propeller acts on the flow over the surface. For that, the correlation length definition is used [16, 22, 23]:

$$L_y = \int_0^\infty \sqrt{\gamma^2(f, \eta_y)} d\eta_y, \quad (3)$$

where η_y is the distance between the measurement points, and γ^2 is the coherence, a normalized ratio between the spectral densities of two signals defined as:

$$\gamma^2(\omega) = \frac{|S_{i,j}|^2}{S_{i,i}(\omega)S_{j,j}(\omega)}, \quad (4)$$

and $S(i, j)(\omega)$ is the cross-spectral density (auto-spectral density for $i = j$). The spanwise correlation length is used for problems involving turbulent structures of boundary layers.

The correlation length increases in the downstream direction. This is shown in Figure 9. That is expected as the propeller rotation inserts high turbulent structures and vorticity in the incoming flow. However, there is a difference between the behavior of the correlation length on the plate left side ($0 < y/D < -0.5$, blade rotating away from the plate) and on the right side ($0 < y/D < +0.5$, blade rotating towards the plate). The right side has an increase in correlation length at $x/D = -0.374$. Another interesting observation is the rapid decay on the high frequencies of the higher correlation length position, as can be seen for the $x/D = -0.498$ on the left and $x/D = -0.374$ on the right side of the plate.

Figure 9: Correlation length with streamwise position (2-bladed propeller, 6000 rpm, $J = 0.98$, $\delta/D = 0.18$).

Figures 10 and 11 show the results for different boundary layer sizes and regions of the plate. The propeller does not have a strong influence on the incoming flow. Apart from the tones of the blade passing frequencies, the correlation lengths are similar to the boundary layer without the propeller. The higher frequencies show a spatial periodicity on the L_y for the thicker boundary layers. This happens since the tripped boundary layer is inherently turbulent and has a strong interaction with the propeller complex turbulent and vortical structures.

The same behavior for higher frequencies can be observed downstream of the propeller (Figure 11). There is now a clear difference in correlation length based on the boundary layer thickness impinging on the propeller. Between $\delta/D = 0.18$ and $\delta/D = 0.34$ the correlation length increases through all the frequency ranges analyzed. For $\delta/D = 0.46$, however, a decrease in comparison with $\delta/D = 0.34$ is seen due to the homogeneity of the propeller immersion. Near 50%

Figure 10: Correlation length with comparison between BLI immersions (2-bladed propeller, 6000 rpm, $J = 0.98$). Dashed line is the $\delta/D = 0.46$ boundary layer.

immersion of the disk area, the blades' interaction with the inflow is uniform (both in loading and in turbulent interactions) when compared to smaller disk area immersions.

Figure 11: Correlation length with comparison between BLI immersions (2-bladed propeller, 6000 rpm, $J = 0.98$). Dashed line is the $\delta/D = 0.46$ boundary layer.

5. CONCLUSIONS

An experimental study was carried in wind tunnel tests for a propeller in configuration of boundary layer ingestion. The propeller is set inside an incoming boundary layer, to mimic complex airframe-propulsion conditions. An instrumented flat plate acquires unsteady and static pressures. The static pressure results show how different regions underneath the propeller are affected. Pressure oscillations caused by the propeller rotation are not the only effect, as is seen from vortical structures and the propeller influence on the incoming flow pressure. The complexity of the interactions calls for a further study of the flow underneath the blades. Smoke visual tests can be used in the future for a better understanding of the propeller influence on the surface pressure. The unsteady pressure shows

the regions of influence of the propeller on the turbulent structures of the flow. Downstream there is an increase in the correlation length of the turbulent structures inflicted by the propeller. This increase is dependent on the direction of rotation of the propeller. The changes in the correlation length for the blade rotating towards the plate are not related with boundary layer thickness. Additionally, the tripping exerts a turbulent characteristic on the boundary layer, influencing the results. Therefore, more boundary layer characteristics are necessary to actively quantify the effect. The influence of the propeller on the incoming boundary layer is shown. Those results are applicable for design studies about noise surface mitigators for complex propulsive-airframe interactions such as propellers close to the airframe.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors acknowledge the technical team of the University of Twente, Ing. W. Lette, S. Wanrooij and Ir. E. Leusink for their support in the setup, and of Ir. L. Botero Bolivar and Ir. F.L. Dos Santos for the extensive support in the calibration procedure.

The authors acknowledge *European Union's Horizon 2020* research and innovation program under grant agreement no. 860103 (ENODISE), for the funding and support. The authors also acknowledge SilentProp for providing the propeller geometry for this research.

REFERENCES

1. Nicolas GM Moirou, Drewan S Sanders, and Panagiotis Laskaridis. Advancements and prospects of boundary layer ingestion propulsion concepts. *Progress in Aerospace Sciences*, 138:100897, 2023.
2. B Magliozzi, DB Hanson, and RK Amiet. Propeller and propfan noise. *Aeroacoustics of flight vehicles: theory and practice*, 1:1–64, 1991.
3. Heye Xiao, Tianyue Yuan, Xiang Song, Junli Chen, Jie Zhou, Dan Sui, and Jintao Gu. Broadband sound absorption of subwavelength porous meta-liner. *Frontiers in Materials*, 9:845597, 2022.
4. Daniel J Fritsch, Vidya Vishwanathan, K Todd Lowe, and William J Devenport. Fluctuating pressure beneath smooth wall boundary layers in nonequilibrium pressure gradients. *AIAA Journal*, 60(8):4725–4743, 2022.
5. Shubham Shubham, Richard D Sandberg, Stéphane Moreau, and Hao Wu. Surface pressure spectrum variation with mach number on a cd airfoil. *Journal of Sound and Vibration*, 526:116762, 2022.
6. Liam Hanson, Kabilan Baskaran, Bin Zang, and Mahdi Azarpeyvand. Acoustic shielding and scattering effects of a propeller mounted above a flat plate. In *51st International Congress and Exposition on Noise Control Engineering*. Institute of Noise Control Engineering, 2022.
7. Leandro A Castelucci, Cornelis H Venner, and Leandro D de Santana. Experimental analysis of the noise of small propellers subjected to non-uniform inflow. In *AIAA SCITECH 2023 Forum*, page 1545, 2023.
8. Yaoyi Guan, Carl R Berntsen, Michael J Bilka, and Scott C Morris. The measurement of unsteady surface pressure using a remote microphone probe. *JoVE (Journal of Visualized Experiments)*, page e53627, 2016.
9. Matthew Gazella, Tamuto Takakura, Daniel L Sutliff, Richard Bozak, and Brian J Tester. Evaluating the acoustic benefits of over-the-rotor acoustic treatments installed on the advanced noise control fan. In *23rd AIAA/CEAS Aeroacoustics Conference*, page 3872, 2017.
10. Lennart S Hultgren, Devin K Boyle, and Brenda S Henderson. Dgen aeropropulsion research turbofan source-diagnostic test: Experimental setup and acoustic-data structure. Technical report, 2020.

11. H-C Shin, WR Graham, Pieter Sijtsma, Christodoulos Andreou, and Andrew C Faszer. Implementation of a phased microphone array in a closed-section wind tunnel. *AIAA journal*, 45(12):2897–2909, 2007.
12. Abbas Afshari, Mahdi Azarpeyvand, Ali A Dehghan, Máté Szőke, and Reza Maryami. Trailing-edge flow manipulation using streamwise finlets. *Journal of Fluid Mechanics*, 870:617–650, 2019.
13. Fernanda L Dos Santos, Laura Botero-Bolívar, Cornelis Venner, and Leandro D de Santana. Study of the remote microphone probetechnique for measuring wall-pressurefluctuations. *Springer Nature (Submitted)*, 2023.
14. SP Gravante, AM Naguib, CE Wark, and HMm Nagib. Characterization of the pressure fluctuations under a fully developed turbulent boundary layer. *AIAA journal*, 36(10):1808–1816, 1998.
15. Fernanda L Dos Santos, Laura Botero-Bolívar, Cornelis Venner, and Leandro D de Santana. Influence of roughness trips on near-and far-field trailing-edge noise. *AIAA journal*, 60(10):5880–5889, 2022.
16. Michel Roger. Microphone measurements in aeroacoustic installations. *Educational notes, stoen-avt-287, S&T organization*, 2017.
17. Leandro D de Santana, Martinus P Sanders, Cornelis H Venner, and Harry W Hoeijmakers. The utwente aeroacoustic wind tunnel upgrade. In *2018 AIAA/CEAS Aeroacoustics Conference*, page 3136, 2018.
18. Anton Silvestri, Farzin Ghanadi, Maziar Arjomandi, Benjamin Cazzolato, and Anthony Zander. The application of different tripping techniques to determine the characteristics of the turbulent boundary layer over a flat plate. *Journal of Fluids Engineering, Transactions of the ASME*, 140:1–12, 2018. boundarylayerthickness
boundarylayer.
19. K Rengasamy and Alakesh Ch Mandal. Experiments on effective tripping device in a zero pressure gradient turbulent boundary layer. In *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, page 012016. IOP Publishing, 2017.
20. Fernanda L. Dos Santos, Martinus P.J. Sanders, Leandro D. de Santana, and Cornelis H. Venner. Influence of tripping devices in hastening transition in a flat plate submitted to zero and favorable pressure gradients. *AIAA Scitech 2020 Forum*, pages 1–18, 2020.
21. Development of computational and experimental noise assessment and suppression methodologies for the next generation of silent distributed propulsion configurations, 2020. Last accessed 20 April 2023.
22. Fernanda L dos Santos, Laura Botero-Bolívar, Cornelis H Venner, and Leandro D de Santana. Inflow turbulence distortion for airfoil leading-edge noise prediction for large turbulence length scales for zero-mean loading. *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, 153(3):1811–1822, 2023.
23. Dan Palumbo. Determining correlation and coherence lengths in turbulent boundary layer flight data. *Journal of Sound and Vibration*, 331(16):3721–3737, 2012.